

The Atlantic
Testing Platform for
Maritime Robotics

Topic	ICT-09-2019-2020 (H2020)
Acronym	ATLANTIS
Title	The Atlantic Testing Platform for Maritime Robotics: New Frontiers for Inspection and Maintenance of Offshore Energy Infrastructures.
Project number	871571
Delivery date	31.07.2020
Deliverable number	D9.2
Dissemination level	Confidential
Lead Beneficiary	INESC TEC

EPQ - Requirement No. 2

Written by INESC TEC

